

Community Partner Interview, Prompting Questions

1. Could you describe your experience working with the INSPIRE team?
 - a. How often did they meet you?

 - b. Did the team's dynamic appear to change over time?

2. In your opinion, how did the students perform throughout the 4 months?

3. How satisfied are you (and your organization) with the final MVP that has been handed over to you?
 - a. If possible, ask community partner to elaborate on why the team did well on certain aspects, or not well on certain aspects.

4. What is the realistic impact of the MVP created by the Inspire team?